

Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific
Research

University of Baghdad

College of Engineering

Department of Civil Engineering

Questionnaire form

for assessing the causes of delays for residential investment projects

Greetings...

The researcher is preparing research titled " **Assessing Key Delay Causes in Residential Investment Projects Using Fuzzy AHP and Risk Matrix** "

This questionnaire aims to determine the relative importance of the causes that lead to the delay and failure of residential investment projects in Iraq. The goal is to benefit from the research by serving the public sphere. The research requires tangible evidence of residential investment projects in Iraq. The researcher seeks to explore your views on this topic, given your experience in this field, to achieve the intended benefit. Please provide us with your feedback by answering the questions included in the attached questionnaire.

Thank you for your cooperation...with deepest appreciation and gratitude...

Researcher

Aya Ali Hasan

Note

- The information provided will be used for scientific research purposes only.

First: General Information

<u>Working Sector (optional):</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private <input type="checkbox"/> Both	<u>Work Location(optional) :</u>
<u>Years of Experience:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Less than 5 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5 to 10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11 to 15 years <input type="checkbox"/> 16 to 20 years <input type="checkbox"/> More than 21 years	<u>Academic degree:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's (B.Sc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Master's (M.Sc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate (Ph.D) <input type="checkbox"/> Other

Second: evaluate the causes for delaying residential investment projects using Fuzzy AHP.

Please evaluate the relative importance of each of the identified reasons for delaying residential investment projects based on:

(A) The relative importance scale shown in the following table:

Table (1): Linguistic variables used in the response.

Explanation	Fuzzy number	Linguistic variable
Cause i is equally important when compared to cause j.	(1 , 1 , 1)	Equally important
Cause i is of low importance when compared to cause j.	(2 , 3 , 4)	Low important
Cause i is moderately important when compared to cause j.	(4 , 5 , 6)	Medium important
Cause i is highly important when compared to cause j.	(6 , 7 , 8)	High important
Cause i is very highly important when compared to cause j.	(8 , 9 , 10)	Very high important
When compromise is needed.	(1, 2 ,3) (3 , 4, 5) (5 , 6 ,7) (7, 8 ,9)	Intermediate values between the two adjacent judgments
If cause (j) to him the importance of higher from cause (i) it takes this reciprocal number allocated to the cause (i)	The reciprocals, such as 1/2, 1/3, 1/5, 1/7, 1/9, etc., indicate the opposite respectively of the values 2, 3, 5, 7, 9, et.	Reciprocals number

B) The relative importance of each cause for the delay in residential investment projects in Iraq, as well as the method of pairwise comparison used to evaluate these causes.

A check mark (√) is placed below the appropriate level of importance. If the cause on the left is more important than the corresponding cause on the right, place your check mark to the left under your preferred level of importance. If the cause on the right is more important than the corresponding cause on the left, place your check mark to the right under your preferred level of importance. The example below illustrates how to answer:

Question 1: What is the importance of the "Management cause" when compared to the "Environmental cause"?

Question 2: What is the importance of the "Management cause" when compared to the "Social cause"?

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Management		Economic									1
						√		Management		Environmental									2
								Management		Social			√						3
								Management		Political									4
								Management		Technical									5
								Management		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Management		Project location									7
								Management		Organizational									8

In the example, the Management cause is compared with other causes. When comparing the Management cause with the environmental cause, the mark is placed on the left side of the low importance column, meaning that the Management cause is of higher importance than the environmental cause, but to a low degree.

When continuing to compare the Management cause with the social cause, we notice that the mark is placed on the right side under the medium importance column, meaning that the Management cause is of lower importance than the social cause, but to a medium degree. And Table 1 shows Linguistic variables.

- **This statement outlines the pairwise comparisons of the main causes that determine the relative importance of each for causing delays in residential investment projects:**

Based on your knowledge of the current status of residential investment projects in Iraq, how do you evaluate the causes below that result in delays in these projects?

Please mark (√) under the column you choose appropriate.

i) According to the general causes:

1- Management causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Management		Economic									1
								Management		Environmental									2
								Management		Social									3
								Management		Political									4
								Management		Technical									5
								Management		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Management		Project location									7
								Management		Organizational									8

2- Economic causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Economic		Management									1
								Economic		Environmental									2
								Economic		Social									3
								Economic		Political									4
								Economic		Technical									5
								Economic		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Economic		Project location									7
								Economic		Organizational									8

3- Environmental causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Environmental		Management									1
								Environmental		Economic									2
								Environmental		Social									3
								Environmental		Political									4
								Environmental		Technical									5
								Environmental		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Environmental		Project location									7
								Environmental		Organizational									8

4- Social causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Social		Management									1
								Social		Economic									2
								Social		Environmental									3
								Social		Political									4
								Social		Technical									5
								Social		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Social		Project location									7
								Social		Organizational									8

5- Political causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Political		Management									1
								Political		Economic									2
								Political		Environmental									3
								Political		Social									4
								Political		Technical									5
								Political		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Political		Project location									7
								Political		Organizational									8

6- Technical causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Technical		Management									1
								Technical		Economic									2
								Technical		Environmental									3
								Technical		Social									4
								Technical		Political									5
								Technical		Legal causes and legislative regulations									6
								Technical		Project location									7
								Technical		Organizational									8

7- Legal causes and legislative regulations

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Management									1
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Economic									2
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Environmental									3
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Social									4
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Political									5
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Technical									6
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Project location									7
								Legal causes and legislative regulations		Organizational									8

8- Project location causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Project location		Management									1
								Project location		Economic									2
								Project location		Environmental									3
								Project location		Social									4
								Project location		Political									5
								Project location		Technical									6
								Project location		Legal causes and legislative regulations									7
								Project location		Organizational									8

9- Organizational causes

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Organizational		Management									1
								Organizational		Economic									2
								Organizational		Environmental									3
								Organizational		Social									4
								Organizational		Political									5
								Organizational		Technical									6
								Organizational		Legal causes and legislative regulations									7
								Organizational		Project location									8

ii) According to the project stakeholders:

1- Causes of delays related to the owner

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Owner		Consultant									1
								Owner		Contractor									2

2- Causes of delay related to the consultant

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Consultant		Owner									1
								Consultant		Contractor									2

3- Causes of delay related to the contractor

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Contractor		Owner									1
								Contractor		Consultant									2

iii) Resources management

1- Causes of delays related to labor

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Labor		Equipment									1
								Labor		Materials									2

2- Causes of delays related to equipment

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Equipment		Labor									1
								Equipment		Materials									2

3- Causes of delays related to materials

(9) Very high	(8) High to Very high	(7) High	(6) Medium to High	(5) Medium	(4) Low to Medium	(3) Low	(2) Equal to Low	Cause (i)	(1) Equal importance	Cause (j)	(2) Equal to Low	(3) Low	(4) Low to Medium	(5) Medium	(6) Medium to High	(7) High	(8) High to Very high	(9) Very high	Q
								Materials		Labor									1
								Materials		Equipment									2